

YAYASAN CAHAYA SAMUDERA INDONESIA

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Interactive identification key for the Scleractinian genera of Indonesia

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This interactive key was made to assist people interested in identifying Indonesian scleractinian coral to genus level using *in-situ* photographs. Do note that morphology can greatly differ within the same genera and may be confusing at times. Identifications made with this key are tentative, please seek the help of an expert for confirmation. This resource is not meant to replace the great work of others, such as the Coral Finder (Kelley, 2022) or Corals of the World (Veron, 2000), but to supplement them by assisting users to learn genera identification through a process of elimination. This is a work in progress and will be updated with more genera, new photographs, descriptions, and revised nomenclature in the future. Future versions will also contain images to visually demonstrate each key choice and will be translated to Bahasa Indonesia. Photographs and diagrams are by Febrienne Sukiato unless otherwise credited.

To contact the authors, please fill the contact information form [available on our website](#).

[Click here](#) for a guide to take appropriate photographs for scleractinian identification.

[Click here](#) for a glossary of terms used.

[Click here](#) for an index of all the genera included.

[Click here](#) for a list of references used in this key.

[Click here](#) for the interactive key hosted on Google forms (work in progress).

Version 1 available online as of 16 April 2026.

Solitary attached/detached or colonial

- Coral is a single, free-living disc, otherwise known as a mushroom coral. Smaller corals may still be attached to substrate > [Free-living genera](#)
- Tiny, free-living cup corals with a flat base, often with a hole for a commensal worm > [Heterocyathus or Heteropsammia](#)
- Only one polyp is present attached to the substrate, with one polyp per skeleton > [Isolated attached polyps](#)
- 1-5 cup-shaped polyps attached to the substrate > [Cup-shaped polyps](#)
- Coral is an attached colony (many polyps joined together on substrate) > [Attached colony](#)

Free-living genera

Look for a single round/disc coral, often with radiating ridges or a smooth umbrella shape; it can move slightly when turned by a surge. Juveniles may still be attached to the substrate.

- Circular/disc shaped, may be slightly irregular > [Free-living – disc shaped](#)
- Oblong/oval shaped > [Free-living – oblong/oval shaped](#)
- Long oblong/boomerang/X or Y shaped > [Free-living - Long oblong/boomerang/X or Y shaped](#)
- Thin plates or domes - [Free-living – thin plates or domes](#)
- Rounded disc with daytime extended tentacles > [Heliofungia fralinae & actiniformis](#)
- Tiny, free-living cup corals with a flat base, often with a hole for a commensal worm > [Heterocyathus or Heteropsammia](#)

Free-living – disc shaped

- Domed disc with very fine septal teeth, with neatly arranged septa > [Lithophyllon repanda, concinna, scabra](#)
- Domed discs with purple edges, visible septal teeth, central slit-like mouth > [Fungia fungites](#)
- Domed discs with a central slit-like mouth, with very toothy septa > [Danafungia horrida and scruposa](#)
- Small (3-8 cm) circular or irregular discs or domes > [Cycloseris vaughani, fragilis, distorta](#)
- An irregular, contorted disc with thick, wavy septa-costae > [Cantharellus](#)
- A rounded or irregular disc with thin, wavy septa-costae > [Pleuractis granulosa, moluccensis](#)
- Thick-walled domed skeletons with corallites that are close together and inclined to colony margins, typically cream/brown in colour. Corallites can either group atop the coral or run down the sides. > [Sandalolitha dentata, robusta](#)

Free-living – oblong/oval shaped

- Septa form thin, wavy patterns radiating from a central slit-like mouth > [Pleuractis moluccensis, paumotensis](#)
- Septa radiate from a thin, slit-like mouth. Major septa have tall tentacular lobes > [Lobactis scutaria](#)
- Slit-like mouth extends along the oval, with toothy septa radiating from the mouth line. May have tentacular lobes. > [Ctenactis albitenticulata, echinata, crassa](#)
- Thick-walled domed skeletons with corallites that are close together and inclined to colony margins, typically cream/brown in colour. Corallites can either group together atop of the coral or run down the sides. > [Sandalolitha dentata, robusta](#)

Free-living - Long oblong/boomerang/X or Y shaped

- Long, extended furrow along the top of the oval, with short septa “dripping” from the furrow. > [Herpolitha limax](#)

- Typically covered with short tentacles, giving it a fuzzy look. When retracted, a long slit-like mouth runs along the middle, and septa are short “rice grains” that run towards the edges of the coral. > [Polyphyllia talpina](#)

Free-living – thin plates or domes

- Corals are typically brown with purple edges, with white mouths that run from the center to the edges of the dome. Sometimes found in broken shards. > [Halomitra pileus](#)
- Sometimes found as shards or domes with a rough texture due to toothy septa. Mouths are likely indistinct, and if visible, mouths are not white in colour. > [Zoopilus echinatus](#)
- Thin plates that can whorl and detach from the substrate. Have smooth-textured running septa-costae radiating from the centre of the colony to the edges, linking small corallites that have pale mouths > [Lithophyllon undulatum](#)
- Thin plates that whorl and can detach from the substrate – may look like the previous coral, but septa-costae are rougher and corallites are slightly inclined to plate edges > [Podabacia](#)

Isolated attached polyps

- Flat, single-polyp “fleshy brain” up to ~6 cm across > [Lobophyllia](#)
- Appears attached but actually just slightly buried in silty substrate. Single polyp with many lobes, and can be very brightly coloured > [Trachyphyllia geoffroyi](#)
- Rounded corallites with large and thick septal blades, tissue around the blades is generally inflated and see-through. Can be very brightly coloured > [Cynarina lacrymalis](#)
- Singular cup-shaped polyps attached to hard substrates, typically 1-2 cm in diameter and usually found in sandy/silty low visibility environments. Typically orange, yellow, or pink > [Balanophyllia](#)
- Singular polyps shaped like squished ovals. Bases are fan-like and buried in silt > [Truncatoflabellum](#)
- One or more cup-shaped polyps attached to a hard substrate, typically in a shade of orange or dark green. > [Tubastrea](#)
- Clumps of one or more cup-shaped polyps attached to a hard substrate. Usually found in crevices or walls without much light exposure. Typically dull yellowish-orange to pink coloured. Single polyps may run rhizome-like structures and link with other nearby polyps > [Cladopsammia gracilis](#)
- One or more small white cup-shaped polyps attached to hard substrate in areas without much light > [Thalamophyllia tenuescens](#)
- Looks like a large irregularly shaped fungiid attached to hard substrate; mouth not always visible, and septa can overlap and clash > [Pleuractis moluccensis](#)
- With extended daytime tentacles/inflated tissues > [Section Large fleshy polyps/tentacled corals](#)

Cup-shaped polyps

Members of Dendrophyllidae and Caryophyllidae are famously difficult to identify even to the genus level. These azooxanthellate corals tend to form in low-light areas such as caves and overhangs.

These are characterised by their conical, cup-shaped corallites, with tentacles extended usually at night. Colourations may vary from greens, oranges, yellows, pinks, to greys.

- Form tall, branching colonies, typically dark green to near black. Can form in lower reef slopes. > [Tubastrea micranthus](#)
- Form short branching colonies, typically olive-greenish in colour. Can form in lower reef slopes. > [Tubastrea diaphana](#)
- Form stout, near spherical colonies with corallite cups jutting out, typically yellow to orange in colour. Typically found in low-light areas. > [Tubastrea coccinea](#)
- One or more small white cup-shaped polyps attached to hard substrate in areas without much light > [Thalamophyllia](#)
- Singular cup-shaped polyps attached on hard substrates, typically 1-2 cm in diameter and usually found in sandy/silty low visibility environments. Typically orange, yellow, or pink > [Balanophyllia](#)
- Singular polyps shaped like squished ovals. Bases are fan-like and buried in silt. > [Truncatoflabellum](#)
- Tiny, free-living cup corals with a flat base, often with a hole for a commensal worm > [Heterocyathus](#) or [Heteropsammia](#)

Attached colony

- Colony shows large, fleshy polyps or long tentacles that are often visible during the day (often with bulbous tips, hammer-shape, or long feeding tentacles). Sometimes, tentacles can be retracted, giving the colony a fuzzy appearance > [Large fleshy polyps/tentacled corals](#)
- Colony does not show large conspicuous tentacles – surface looks mostly skeletal (small bumps or obvious branches/plates) > [Colony shape – branches or projections](#)

Large fleshy polyps/tentacled corals

These corals often look fleshy, almost like soft coral, and the individual polyps are obvious even from a few metres. Often called “bubble corals”. Other genera in this category have very puffy, raised tissues. Sometimes, tentacles can be retracted, giving the colony a fuzzy appearance or revealing their skeletons.

- Stringy and straight tentacles. When retracted, reveal stalked corallites that branch out from a base. > [Euphyllia](#)
- Odd-shaped and unique vesicles, may have kidney or other irregularly shaped tips. When tentacles are retracted, they reveal stalked branches or meandering walls from an encrusting base. > [Fimbriaphyllia](#)
- Grape-like rounded or teardrop-shaped vesicles. When tentacles are retracted, they reveal stalked branches or meandering walls from an encrusting base. > [Plerogyra](#)
- Small (~5 mm) grape-like vesicles cover the colony. When tentacles are retracted, they reveal meandering lines of valleys formed by septal blades. Colonies are massive and can be hillocky > [Physogyra lichtensteini](#)
- Short or long polyps extend from the base, which can be massive, plating, branching, or columnar. Each polyp has 24 tentacles. Tentacle tips are long and wispy. When polyps are retracted, the colony may look like a fuzzy *Porites*. > [Goniopora](#)

- Short or long polyps extend from the base, which can be massive, plating, or branching. Each polyp has 12 tentacles. Tentacles are shorter and more rounded than *Goniopora*. When polyps are retracted, the colony may look like a fuzzy Porites. > [Alveopora](#)
- Rounded isolated corallites with large septal blades, tissue around the blades is generally inflated and see through. Can be very brightly coloured > [Cynarina](#)
- May look like *Goniopora*, but tentacles are shorter when fully extended and tend to have tentacle sharper tips. When fully retracted, colony may look like fuzzy encrusting/plating Porites. > [Bernardpora](#)
- Form thick plates, may form large groups of plates. Immersed cup-shaped corallites are found on the horizontal, upwards facing sides. When tentacles are expanded, give the colony a fuzzy carpet look. > [Duncanopsammia](#)
- Encrusting coral with large, fleshy polyps. May look like a puffy zoanthid at first glance. Typically fluorescent colouring. > [Blastomussa](#)
- Can be branching, encrusting, or massive with a fuzzy carpet of tentacles on the surface. When retracted, colonies show distinctive conical bumps or ridges. > [Hydnophora](#)
- Corallites form spiky calices jutting out from an encrusting base, with tentacles surrounding each calice. > [Galaxea fascicularis, astreata, paucisepta](#)

Colony shape – branches or projections

- Branching, finger-like, or club-like > [Branching, finger-like, or club-like projections](#)
- Colonies have thick columns that jut out from an encrusting base (base may or may not be visible) > [Column-like projections](#)
- Other growth forms (massive, encrusting, plates) > [Other growth forms](#)

Branching, finger-like, or club-like projections

Colonies that grow upright branches or clubs.

- Branches always have distinct axial corallites at the tip and radial corallites that run down the length of the branch. Comes in a variety of growth forms: branching, tabular, corymbose, bottle-brush, etc. > [Acropora](#)
- Very small corallites (1-2 mm) and some species can be deceptively smooth-looking. Form finger-like branches with knobby/blunted ends. In some species, corallites may be sunken into walls and may look like they share walls, so they can be confused with *Montipora*. > [Porites cylindrica, attenuata, deformis, nigricens](#)
- Form finger-like projections. Very small corallites (1-2 mm) with less defined walls than Porites and generally look rougher than Porites due to the presence of ridges and spines. > [Montipora](#)
- Form thin finger-like branches and may look deceptively like *Porites*. When tentacles are retracted, the colony reveal distinctive, star-shaped corallites. > [Palauastrea ramosa](#)
- A distinctive rounded axial corallite with radial corallites along the branch – frequently confused as *Acropora*. Note the many incipient axial corallites. This look is easily recognisable once you learn. > [Isopora brueggemanni](#)
- Thin, tapered branches with pointed or rounded ends. Many small radial corallites that are generally widely spaced. Corallite openings are not visible to the naked eye. > [Anacropora](#)

- Fine branches with pointed or slightly blunted tips. Corallites have slight hoods and align in neat lines along the branches. > [Seriatopora](#)
- Branches have elongated running ridges along their length. Conical bumps or ridges are visible when tentacles are retracted. When tentacles are extended, colony can look fuzzy. > [Hydnophora rigida](#)
- Branches are crooked fingers (“Witch fingers”), typically yellow to dark brown in colouration. Characteristic spiny lines of bumps on corallites that radiate out from the mouths. > [Echinopora horrida](#)
- Very fine spiny branches. Each corallite is surrounded by spiky septa. > [Galaxea horrescens](#)
- Form tall branching colonies, typically dark green to near black. Can form in lower reef slopes. > [Tubastrea micranthus](#)
- Encrusting bases that grow tall, skinny, and smooth-looking branches (“french fries”). Oval-shaped mouths are interspersed between the base and along the branches. > [Pectinia paeonia, teres](#)
- Thin branches with exert circular corallites and visible septa that radiate out. Spaces between corallites have small skeletal bumps. > [Cyphastrea](#)
- Knobby, smooth-looking branches. Corallites are very small but zoomed-in pictures reveal flower-like patterns of septa surrounding each mouth. > [Psammocora](#)
- Stalk-like branches. When tightly packed together, grow into a sub-massive growth form. > [Caulastrea](#) and [Astreosmilia](#)
- Form knobby branches or clubs that can form into submassive colonies. Upon closer inspection, present spikes vertically above each corallite. > [Stylophora](#)
- Knobby branches or clubs that can form into submassive colonies. Some species have characteristic bumps (verrucae), but others do not. Generally very fuzzy due to extended daytime tentacles. > [Pocillopora](#)

Column-like projections

Colonies with thick, column-like branches arising from an encrusting base.

- Thick upright columns or clubs, often with a flared base; axial corallites are absent (branch tips blunt). Corallites are rounded crescents, like bitten donuts. > [Isopora palifera and cuneata](#)
- Large flat columns with bumps called verrucae, with small corallites located on and between verrucae > [Pocillopora grandis](#)
- Colonies usually over 1 m in diameter, with small (3-4.5 mm diameter) spiky corallites. Can form tall columns. > [Galaxea astreata](#)
- Colonies have an encrusting base and form tall columns. Meandering ridges are rounded, and have a zipper-like texture. Ridges are perpendicularly angled to the edge of the colony. > [Merulina cylindrica](#)
- Large columns form hemispherical submassive colonies and can form large monotypic fields. Corallites are indented and have septa-costal systems that run between corallites. > [Pavona clavus and duerdeni](#)
- Large columns form hemispherical submassive colonies. Upon closer inspection, corallites do not have distinct walls, but have small (1 mm) rice grain patterns. > [Psammocora haimiana](#)

Other growth forms

- Encrusting or massive on hard substrate > [Encrusting or massive on hard substrate](#)
- Encrusting base with projecting plates/tables that may stack > [Encrusting base with plate projections](#)
- Foliose/vase like – colonies form curled, thin plates > [Foliose/vase-like](#)

Encrusting or massive on hard substrate

- Corallites with separate walls > [Encrusting/massive – separate walls](#)
- Corallites with shared walls > [Encrusting/massive – shared walls](#)
- Corallites within meandroid walls > [Encrusting/massive – meandroid walls](#)
- Corallites with indistinct walls > [Encrusting/massive – indistinct walls](#)

Encrusting/massive – separate walls

Each corallite is distinct with its own wall.

- Corallites form like miniature volcanoes without any space in between, and do not point at a specific direction giving the colony a “googly-eyed” look. Spiny beads radiate out of the mouth of each corallite. > [Astreopora](#) - **encrusting massives**
- Colonies are encrusting and may have slight lifting at edges, forming plates. Corallites are circular and distinct, with characteristic spiny look to each corallite. Usually in brown, cream, or yellow. > [Echinopora gemmacea, pacificus](#)
- Small, evenly spaced corallites that are round and neatly separated. Exsert corallites are uniformly spaced across the colony, and spaces between corallites have a bumpy texture if the coral is not inflated. > [Cyphastrea](#)
- Very small, tightly packed corallites forming a fine, granular surface. Corallites are shallow and closely spaced, giving a smooth but slightly pitted texture. Septa of corallites alternate in length, giving it a starry look. > [Leptastrea](#)
- Corallites are round to slightly angular and closely packed, each with its own wall but sharing edges. Characteristically have paliform lobes. > [Goniastrea](#)
- Forms large, heavy colonies with thick lobes and ridges. Corallites are broad and fleshy, often merging into short valleys, giving it a “meaty” appearance. Surface appears swollen and irregular. Sometimes submassive, with long stalks topped with a fleshy polyp. > [Lobophyllia](#)
- Thin, delicate colonies that may be encrusting or plating. Corallites are small and scattered, often sitting on a slightly rough or uneven surface. Overall colony looks lightweight and fragile, sometimes with wavy margins. Corallites can be well defined, or very messy. Sometimes confused with *Echinopora* or *Echinophyllia*. > [Oxypora](#)
- Very fine corallites that are difficult to distinguish individually, giving a smooth, sandpaper-like texture. Each corallite has a spike next to it. > [Stylocoeniella quentheri, armata](#)
- Corallites are round and well-defined, each with thick walls. Centres are often deep and contrasting in colour. Sometimes has a mottled colouration. > [Dipsastraea](#)
- Compact, rounded corallites with deep grooves between corallites. Incredibly variable genus. > [Favites](#)
- Circular corallites vary in size and appear crowded (tightly packed). Septa sizes strongly alternate in size. > [Astrea curta](#)

- Encrusting to submassive colony with small, raised corallites. Between the corallites, the surface texture of the colony looks smooth. > [Turbinaria stellatus](#)
- Small, round corallites that are clearly separated but closely packed. Each corallite has a thick rim and deep centre, giving a neat “button-like” pattern across the colony. Often forms compact encrusting patches. > [Oulastrea](#)
- Stalk-like branches. When tightly packed together, grow into a sub-massive growth form. > [Caulastrea](#) and [Astreosmilia](#)
- Thick upright columns or clubs, often with a flared base; axial corallites are absent (branch tips blunt). Corallites are rounded crescents, like bitten donuts. > [Isopora palifera](#) and [cuneata](#)
- Corallites form little mounds with thick septa-costae radiating out of the corallite mouth. Distinctive look to this species. Typically brown with white mouths. > [Diploastrea heliopora](#)

Encrusting/massive – shared walls

Corallites share common walls.

- Corallites share walls and form rounded to polygonal shapes. Colony appears like tightly packed cells, sometimes transitioning toward short valleys. Have a characteristic “raggedy” look. > [Platygyra](#)
- Surface covered in small rice-shaped bumps. Corallites are poorly defined and often fused, giving a rough, uneven texture without clear pattern.> [Psammocora](#)
- Corallites are tightly packed, and form a regular, honeycomb-like pattern. Septa are well-developed and paliform lobes are visible as small projections around the centre of the mouth. > [Goniastrea](#)
- Corallites are irregular in shape and size, giving a less orderly pattern than *Goniastrea*. Septa are fine and closely spaced. Shared walls are often less distinct, giving a smoother surface look. In zoomed in images, dots (short tentacles) lie between septa > [Coeloseria](#)
- Thickly encrusting or massive colonies. Corallites are large (10-20 mm) and deeply concave, and multiple mouths can occur within the same walls. Walls are thinner than shared-wall *Lobophyllia*.> [Oulophyllia benettiae](#)
- Corallites are polygonal, forming a tight, honeycomb-like pattern. Corallite size is less regular than in *Goniastrea*. Septa are well developed and paliform lobes are present. Walls are thicker than *Goniastrea*. > [Favites](#)
- Similar to *Goniastrea* but with more irregularly shaped corallites. Colonies often appear less uniform, with uneven spacing and shapes. > [Paragoniastrea](#)
- Found in low light areas. Colonies are small and encrusting, typically with a pinkish hue. Small corallites share walls are distinctively ridged. > [Madracis](#)
- Large, fleshy polyps sitting in shared skeletal structure. When expanded, polyps dominate the appearance, giving a soft, inflated look. > [Blastomussa](#)
- Large, fleshy corallites with shared walls in places. Skeletal bumps form concentrically around each corallite, visible despite the thick flesh covering, giving it a toothy look. > [Acanthastrea](#)
- Found in turbid areas. Very small, angular, and tightly packed corallites forming a fine, uniform texture. Corallites are typically brown, and walls are a lighter cream colour. > [Pseudosiderastrea tayamai](#)

- Shallow, closely packed corallites that may form low ridges or irregular patterns. Surface appears smooth but subtly textured with fine grain-like structures along the walls. > [*Coscinaraea*](#)
- Form rounded oval spheres with cup-like corallites. Corallites are tubular and clearly separated, often bright orange or yellow. Polyps are large and extend prominently, especially at night. > [*Tubastrea*](#)
- Form massive to encrusting colonies. Corallites are immersed with rounded bottoms (giving a scooped-out look), separated by a sharp “wall”. Septo-costae are fine and even. > [*Gardineroseris planulata*](#)

Encrusting/massive – meandroid walls

Corallites share common walls or form valleys.

- Corallites form winding valleys with shared walls, creating a maze-like (brain coral) pattern. Valleys are usually deep and continuous. Walls have a “ragged” look, which can be distinguishable after observing many colonies of this genus. > [*Platygyra*](#)
- Older colonies are always massive. Narrow, tightly packed valleys forming fine, intricate maze patterns. Ridges are rounded and septal blades overlap, giving it a zipper-like texture. > [*Leptoria*](#)
- Surface is marked by winding valleys separated by thin, uneven ridges, often creating a wrinkled appearance. Ridge valleys are often irregular, often branching, broken or forming short, twisting segments. > [*Merulina scabricula, ampliata*](#)
- Surface has shallow, winding valleys separated by low, rounded ridges. Corallites are small, shallow and often immersed, often arranged along the valleys, giving a subtle maze-like pattern. The ridges are soft and irregular, giving a fine-textured and gentle wrinkled overall appearance > [*Pavona varians*](#)
- Surfaces show shallow, winding valleys with very small (0.5-1mm) immersed corallites often sharing walls along the valley floor. Ridges between valleys are low and finely textured, giving a faint maze-like undulation pattern. > [*Montipora*](#)
- Broad valleys with thick walls, often widely spaced. Valleys appear deeper and more open. > [*Oulophyllia crispa and levis*](#)
- Sharp, blade-like ridges forming thin walls. Valleys are deep and narrow, giving a spiky or jagged appearance. > [*Pectinia lactuca*](#)
- Large, fleshy valleys with thick tissue. Ridges are swollen and irregular, often merging into lobes. > [*Lobophyllia*](#)
- Broad, winding valleys separated by thick, well-defined walls. Walls are robust and evenly spaced, creating a textured, pronounced brain-like surface that is coarser than Montipora or Pavona > [*Coscinaraea*](#)
- Short, triangular ridges bound Corallites and have obvious septo-costae that run perpendicular from ridge margins. Ridges are often meandering and parallel to one another but can form a complex web of opposing ridges. > [*Pachyseris rugosa and speciosa*](#)

Encrusting/massive – indistinct walls

Corallites that are hard to see or indistinct, giving the colony a rough but non-valley texture.

- Corallites are very small (0.5-1mm), shallow and mostly immersed, with walls that are nearly invisible. The surface appears smooth to finely textured, often with subtle bumps or tiny pores, but without clear individual corallite cups. > [Montipora](#)
- Corallites are often irregularly shaped and arranged, giving the colony surface a lumpy appearance. Septa-costa run to other corallite mouths when not interrupted by walls. > [Pavona](#)
- Thin, encrusting to plating colony with a rough surface. Corallites are small and scattered, sometimes raised. Corallite mouths may not be easily distinguishable unless mouths are of a different colour than the rest of the colony. > [Echinophyllia](#)
- Delicate, thin colonies with faint corallites. Surface appears smooth to slightly uneven, often with wavy edges. > [Oxypora](#)
- Very fine corallites that are difficult to distinguish individually, giving a smooth, sandpaper-like texture. Each corallite has a small spike next to it. > [Stylocoeniella](#)
- Corallites are circular and often form a smooth, rounded disc with radial septa extending from the central mouth. The colony surface is relatively even, sometimes slightly domed, without a tight honeycomb pattern. > [Cycloseris](#)
- Colony tightly encrusts the substrate, forming a “mushroom-like” cup shape. Septa are thick and wavy. > [Cantharellus jebbi](#)
- Corallites are irregularly arranged, often forming meandering valleys or plate-like ridges. Colony surface is smooth to slightly undulating. > [Leptoseris](#)
- Colonies are thinly encrusting. Some species may have lightly scooped corallites, and some may have ridges, and others look smooth. Corallites are very small, but zoomed-in pictures reveal flower-like patterns of septa surrounding each mouth. > [Psammocora](#)

Encrusting base with plate projections

Corals that have a flat base that encrusts rock, with upright plates or tiers. The colony grows as a shallow horizontal layer with vertical flanges or whorls.

- Encrusting base with upright plates or branches. Presence of a distinct axial corallite at tips helps distinguish it. > [Acropora table](#)
- Corallites are shallow, circular to oval, and irregularly arranged along the plates. Septa are thin and poorly developed. The colony surface is smooth to slightly undulating, with corallites forming subtle depressions. > [Leptoseris](#)
- Corallites form short valleys or shallow grooves along the plates. Colony surface is uneven or slightly bumpy > [Pavona](#)
- Corallites are circular to oval, irregularly arranged and found only on the upper part of the plate (unifacial), and the surface between corallites is smooth. Plates may be staked or tiered. > [Turbinaria](#)
- Surface between corallites is smooth. Corallites are larger and more widely spaced, and plates are thicker than *Turbinaria*. > [Duncanopsammia](#)
- Corallites are unifacial with prominent, exert blade-like septa visible from underside of plate > [Podabacia](#)
- Encrusting with thick and irregular upright or foliose plate projections, with short, discontinuous valleys or ridges where corallites are partially fused. Corallites may be bifacial. > [Lithophyllon](#)

- Colony forms encrusting base with small, closely spaced, circular to polygonal corallites that are shallow and distinct, not forming valleys. > [Pachyseris](#)
- Corallites form thin, delicate foliose or vase-like plate from an encrusting base, with corallites fully integrated into long, continuous meandroid valleys. Septa are well-developed and aligned perpendicular to the valley axis. Columellae are weak, giving linear, organised valley patterns. > [Oxypora](#)
- Colonies form encrusting base with large, dome-shaped corallites that are mostly discrete, sometimes slightly fused at the margins. Septa are thick, widely spaced, and often ornamented with spines or granules. > [Echinophyllia](#)
- Plates with slightly raised, beaded corallites giving a dotted appearance across the surface.> [Astreopora](#)
- Colonies are encrusting and may have slight lifting at edges, forming plates. Corallites are circular and distinct, with characteristic spiny look to each corallite. Usually in brown, cream, or yellow. > [Echinopora](#)
- Plates that angle upward, with corallites facing outward, often toward the edges. > [Mycedium](#)
- Colonies are thinly encrusting with plate-like projections lifting from the substrate. Sharp, blade-like ridges forming thin walls. Valleys are deep and narrow, giving a spiky or jagged appearance. > [Pectinia](#)
- Smooth plates with very small, uniform corallites. Surface appears fine and even. > [Porites](#)
- Plates with smooth to slightly rough surface. Corallites are very small and not easily seen. > [Montipora](#)

Plates/Foliose/vase-like

Colonies are thin, plate-like or vase-shaped colonies (like plates curling up). These form whorls or stacked plates.

- Colony forms one or more horizontal, plate-like tables often arranged in tiers, with growth occurring outward and slightly upwards from a central base. Presence of single, prominent axial corallite at the tip of each branchlet, surrounded by smaller radial corallites > [Acropora table tiered](#)
- Corallites sit in rectangular pocket between radiating ridges and low walls on the plate, with speto-costae moderately protruding and alternating in pattern. > [Leptoseris yabei](#)
- Thin plates that can tier and slightly curl. Small corallites. Between the corallites, the surface texture of the colony looks smooth. > [Turbinaria renniformis, mesenterina](#)
- Smooth surface between corallites. Corallites are ~6mm. Tentacles are usually extended during the day. > [Duncanopsammia peltata](#)
- Colony forms thin, often whorled plates or upright cups with undulating margins. Distinct, outward-facing (oblique) corallites that are strongly inclined towards the colony margin, each forming a small projecting “tube” with a lip-like lower edge, giving the surface a directional, swept appearance. > [Mycedium robokaki, mancaoi, elephantotus](#)
- Colonies form thin, overlapping or whorled plates with free margins. Corallites are not distinctly separated but merged into a continuous skeletal surface, with strongly exsert, blade-like septa that project and are especially visible on the underside of the plates, giving a rough serrated appearance. > [Podabacia](#)

- Colony forms thick plates or upright cups with irregular, often lobed margins. Surface has short, irregular valleys or ridges where corallites are partially fused (submeandroid), giving a somewhat uneven, ridged appearance. Both surfaces may show corallites > [Lithophyllon](#)
- Colonies are thin plates that can form whorls and layer. Corallites are very small (0.5-1mm), shallow and mostly immersed, with walls that are nearly invisible. The surface appears smooth to finely textured, often with subtle bumps or tiny pores, but without clear individual corallite cups. > [Montipora](#)
- Colony forms thin, whorls or layered plates with sharp, fragile margins. Corallites are fully integrated into long, continuous meandroid valleys. Septa are well-developed and regularly spaced and align perpendicularly to the valley axis and converge toward a weak columella > [Oxypora](#)
- Colonies form thin plates that are arranged in single or multiple tiers. Corallites are ~2-4mm, raised as dome-shaped mounts. Paliform lobes are distinct. Surface between corallites appears gritty or beady > [Echinopora lamellosa](#)
- Corallites are found on upper side of plate (unifacial). Plates are usually horizontal and may develop upright ridges. Corallites appear in multiple rows between the ridges. Colony surface shows concentric ridges parallel to plate margins. > [Pachyseris speciosa](#)
- Irregular, sinuous valleys and ridges that are uneven in width and arrangement, often forming a convoluted network across the surface, with corallites sharing common walls along the valleys. > [Merulina](#)
- Corallites are distinct, round, and sometimes elevated on small cones, with fine septa giving a granular or sandpaper-like surface texture > [Astreopora](#)

In-situ photography for scleractinian identification

Learning coral identification on the fly during a dive is challenging, so this guide recommends that you begin by practicing your photography skills. This also entails that you master neutral buoyancy to avoid placing your hands or fins on any coral or substrate during photography. You do need both hands for this, and hovering is indeed a very valuable skill for a diver!

You need the following things:

- A waterproof camera capable of taking macro photos. I personally use an Olympus TG-7 with a Sea Frogs housing. Action cameras such as GoPro, DJI Osmo, or Insta Ace are not recommended for identification purposes, as they are incapable of focusing on corallite structures without additional (expensive) lenses.
- A ruler, or anything that can provide a scale. Scales are critical for identifying certain corals to genus level, and some can be identified to species just from the size of their corallites or structures. If you forgot your ruler, you could always use your fingernail.
- Buoyancy control and understanding of lighting angles. Lighting is important to highlight corallite structures, and when you are casting a shadow on the coral, this darkens the overall image and hide important information.
- That being said: lighting. You can use your inbuilt camera flash or purchase external lighting. I use the X-Adventure RL3000 ring light, though many others utilise torches or strobes.

Ensure that you take pictures of the coral colony with the following angles:

1. A wide shot showing coral growth form
2. A mid shot showing the relation between corallites (necessity if corallites are very large, ideally have a scale)
3. Close up shot of colony structures (have a scale!)

When done well, you should get photos like this:

<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407647>

From here, we can determine that the colony has:

- An attached, encrusting growth form
- Shared walls, with some corallites merging within the same walls, forming a slight meandroid pattern
- Corallites have paliform lobe structures near its mouth

Leading to the conclusion that it is a *Goniastrea* sp. Try it out yourself!

Glossary

Scleractinian colony growth forms

Branching

Colonies form tree-like branches stemming from a main branch. Branches can fuse together, forming tables.

Encrusting

Corals grow as a layer on the surface. Do note that all corals begin as encrusting juveniles, and later develop other growth forms.

Massive

Colonies form small (submassive) or large round domes or mounds, often growing to huge sizes (over 1 m).

Plating

Colonies are encrusting and form plate-like projections at the edges, lifting above the substrate.

Foliose

Colonies grow structures of thin and flat swirled plates that appear rose or cabbage-like.

Solitary

Corals that grow with a single corallite and polyp. Can be attached or free-living.

Free-Living

Corals that have detached from hard substrate and live loosely on the sea floor or may be slightly submersed in soft substrate. Can be moved by wave action. Can inflate their tissues to move about or have some other form of movement. NOTE: Do not handle corals unless you have business with it!

Corallite and polyp diagram

Corallite structures

Corallite

Cup-like structures in a coral's skeleton that houses an individual coral polyp. Sometimes, corallite structures are visible through the coral tissue. Other times, skeletal samples must be examined microscopically to determine features.

Septa

Thin vertical blades in a coral's skeleton that radially surround a corallite, inside the walls of the corallite.

Costae

Thin vertical blades in a coral's skeleton that radially surround a corallite, outside the walls of the corallite. Not typically present in corals that share walls.

Wall

A raised skeletal structure separating the inside of a corallite from the outside of a corallite. Also separates the inner vertical blades (septa) from the outer vertical blades (septo-costae). Walls can be shallow (indistinct) or very obvious and can be breached by continuous vertical blades (septo-costae).

Septo-costae

Refers to skeletal ridges that radiate out from the center of the corallite and is both the septa and costae together, separated by the wall.

Separate walls

Corallites have walls that are separated by an obvious valley or very large gap. Present clear septa and costae.

Shared walls

Colonies where the wall between corallites is the same with no distinct separation or structure in between. Septa run from one corallite to the next, and costae are absent.

Paliform lobes

Small, raised skeletal structure inside a corallite on the centre septa. Usually pointy and cylindrical, visible through the coral's tissues.

No or indistinct walls

Colonies have very shallow walls that only appear as low ridges. Sometimes, corallites are difficult to distinguish. Sometimes, mouths are also small and hidden.

Running septo-costae

In corallites that have suppressed or indistinct walls, corallites can be linked by visible septo-costae that "run" from one corallite mouth to the other.

Appressed/immersed corallite

A corallite that grows sunken or level to the surrounding skeletal structures.

Exsert/emersed corallite

A corallite that grows outside a skeleton with an emerging structure, such as large walls.

Polyp structures

Polyp

An individual living coral organism composed of fleshy tissue. Polyps asexually reproduce forming clones to build colonies.

Tentacles

Flexible, fleshy appendages surrounding a polyp's mouth. Tentacles have nematocytes (stinging cells) to capture prey and bring it to the polyp's mouth. For most corals, tentacles are extended at night, but some genera have tentacles extended during the day as well.

Mouth

A central opening of the coral polyp that takes in food and expels waste. Can be retractable.

Oral disc

Top, flattened circle in the middle of the polyp. The mouth is at the centre. May be a different colour than the rest of the corallite.

Vesicle

A fleshy tentacle-like appendage that can be inflated. Usually a round sack filled with water that may be retractable.

Arrangements of corallites

Axial corallite

A corallite that grows at the tip of a branch, in the same line as the centre, the axis, of a branch.

Radial corallite

A corallite that grows around the sides, in the same line as the centre, radially, of a branch.

Unifacial

Corallites are present on only one side of the coral's skeleton.

Bifacial

Corallites are present on both sides of the coral's skeleton.

Meandroid

Colonies that contain multiple corallites inside ridges or walls, usually in the form of short or long continuous valleys.

Substrates

Hard substrate

Immovable, fixed in place structure on the seafloor like rocks, rubble, or boulders.

Soft substrate

Movable, shifting materials on the seafloor like sand or silt.

List of genera

Future versions will include descriptions for each genera, as well as known spawning patterns.

Acanthastrea

Family: [Lobophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Acanthastrea](#)

Shared walls

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330203987>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/285006014>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/329140952>

Acropora

Family: [Acroporidae](#)

Genus: [Acropora](#)

Arborescent

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333833857>

Hispidose

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333835054>

Corymbose plate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333699475>

Open table

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333925440>

Fused tables

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333835051>

Digitate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333691739>

Alveopora

Family: [Acroporidae](#)

Genus: [Alveopora](#)

Alveopora spongiosa cf.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/321366682>

Other *Alveopora*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/285006007>

Anacropora

Family: [Acroporidae](#)

Genus: [Anacropora](#)

Thin branching

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/280998422>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/252120614>

Astrea

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Astrea](#)

Astrea curta

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330206063>

Astreopora

Family: [Acroporidae](#)

Genus: [Astreopora](#)

Massive separate walls

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269093191>

Plate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/280984959>

Astreaosmilia

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Astraeosmilia](#)

Astraeosmilia curvata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407629>

Astraeosmilia maxima

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/349318984>

Balanophyllia

Family: [Dendrophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Balanophyllia](#)

Isolated attached

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360667>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335226930>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360675>

Bernardpora

Family: [Poritidae](#)

Genus: [Bernardpora](#)

Bernardpora stutchburyi

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283348532>

Blastomussa

Family: [Plerogyridae](#)

Genus: [Blastomussa](#)

Blastomussa wellsi or *vivida*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952801>

Cantharellus

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Cantharellus](#)

Cantharellus noumeae or *Pleuractis mollucensis*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/285006012>

Cantharellus jebbi

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330201292>

Caulastrea

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Caulastraea](#)

Caulastraea furcata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/244424160>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/237618730>

Cladopsammia

Family: [Dendrophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Cladopsammia](#)

Cladopsammia gracilis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042099>

Coeloseris

Family: [Euphyllidae](#)

Genus: [Coeloseris](#)

Coeloseris mayeri

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092165>

Coscinaraea

Family: [Coscinaraeidae](#)

Genus: [Coscinaraea](#)

Coscinaraea crassa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/302301138>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/280984914>

Ctenactis

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Ctenactis](#)

Ctenactis albitenticulata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952455>

Ctenactis echinata or crassa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325027280>

Cycloseris

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Cycloseris](#)

Cycloseris vaughani

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042429>

Cycloseris cyclolites

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360736>

Cycloseris fragilis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/285006009>

Cycloseris mokai

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325027375>

Cycloseris explanulata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/280984885>

Cynarina

Family: [Lobophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Cynarina](#)

Cynarina lacrymalis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/295027167>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/244424141>

Cyphastrea

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Cyphastrea](#)

Cyphastrea decadia

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/252120622>

Massive/encrusting *Cyphastrea*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092069>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325026941>

Danafungia

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Danafungia](#)

Danafungia horrida

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/324160808>

Danafungia scruposa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325026856>

Diploastrea

Family: [Diploastraeidae](#)

Genus: [Diploastrea](#)

A monotypic genus.

Diploastrea heliopora

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/240906212>

Dipsastrea

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Dipsastraea](#)

Separate corallites

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360689>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328560803>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322205073>

Duncanopsammia

Family: [Dendrophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Duncanopsammia](#)

Duncanopsammia peltata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330176239>

Echinophyllia

Family: [Lobophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Echinophyllia](#)

Plate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328560901>

Foliose

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322536909>

Encrusting

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952929>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328576617>

Echinopora

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Echinopora](#)

Echinopora horrida

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325027268>

Echinopora lamellosa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042450>

Echinopora gemmacea

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325026921>

Echinopora pacificus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/323988919>

Euphyllia

Family: [Euphyllidae](#)

Genus: [Euphyllia](#)

Euphyllia cristata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/302301133>

Euphyllia glabrescens

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/291466331>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/245390856>

Favites

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Favites](#)

Separate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/282332253>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/279232859>

Shared

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360747>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952774>

Fimbriaphyllia

Family: [Euphyllidae](#)

Genus: [Fimbriaphyllia](#)

Fimbriaphyllia ancora

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360783>

Fimbriaphyllia divisa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/236218428>

Fimbriaphyllia paraancora

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/291466343>

Fimbriaphyllia paradivisa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/243098409>

Fimbriaphyllia yaeyamensis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/244424075>

Fungia

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Fungia](#)

Fungia fungites

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328599051>

Galaxea

Family: [Euphyllidae](#)

Genus: [Galaxea](#)

Galaxea horrescens

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283348609>

Galaxea fascicularis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325113826>

Galaxea paucisepta cf.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328576551>

Galaxea astreata cf.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952409>

Galaxea longisepta

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/326158491>

Gardineroseris

Family: [Agariciidae](#)

Genus: [Gardineroseris](#)

A monotypic genus.

Gardineroseris planulata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042459>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/245390832>

Goniastrea

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Goniastrea](#)

Separate walls

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322205139>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952401>

Shared walls

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/242689127>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/242689149>

Goniopora

Family: [Poritidae](#)

Genus: [Goniopora](#)

- Retracted tentacles: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092620>
- Extended tentacles: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/280984816>

Halomitra

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Halomitra](#)

Halomitra pileus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322403734>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/326158526>

Heliofungia

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Heliofungia](#)

Heliofungia actiniformis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328560483>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328560456>

Heliofungia fralinae

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283379434>

Herpolitha

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Herpolitha](#)

Herpolitha limax

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407633>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/286541684>

Heterocyathus and Heteropsammia

Family: [Caryophylliidae](#) and [Dendrophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Heterocyathus](#) and [Heteropsammia](#)

Description: Small, free-living, cup shaped corals. Both genera have a flat base with holes at the bottom, which is where a commensal worm lives. The worms assist the coral to move across the substrate.

Heteropsammia cochlea (c) febr

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/256592336>

Heterocyathus aequicostatus (c) Vincent Chalias

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/292302094>

Hydnopora

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Hydnophora](#)

Hydnophora rigida

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407697>

Hydnophora exesa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330206076>

Hydnophora microconos

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322205136>

Isopora

Family: [Acroporidae](#)

Genus: [Isopora](#)

Isopora cuneata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952932>

Isopora palifera

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325027270>

Isopora brueggemanni

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/325027384>

Leptastrea

Family: [Leptastreidae](#)

Genus: [Leptastrea](#)

Massive/encrusting

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/242689200>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/324160798>

Leptoria

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Leptoria](#)

Leptoria phrygia

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952562>

Leptoseris

Family: [Agariciidae](#)

Genus: [Leptoseris](#)

Foliose

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952926>

Plate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330206006>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328599034>

Encrusting

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330207523>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330207523>

Lithophyllon

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Lithophyllon](#)

Disc – free living

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/242689024>

Irregularly shaped

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283348604>

Plate shaped

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283348451>

Lobactis

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Lobactis](#)

Lobactis scutaria

- Juvenile: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/244424097>
- Adult: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092865>

Lobophyllia

Family: [Lobophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Lobophyllia](#)

Isolated attached

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360753>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/329141101>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952772>

Submassive – separate walls

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328576573>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322536903>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/240906225>

Shared walls

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330206049>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042290>

Shared walls – *Lobophyllia rowleyensis*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322205065>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407650>

massive – Meandroid

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952825>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952886>

Submassive – meandroid

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407673>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092039>

Madracis

Family: [Pocilloporidae](#)

Genus: [Madracis](#)

Madracis kirbyi

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283348582>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952931>

Merulina

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Merulina](#)

Merulina scabricula

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328560503>

Merulina ampliata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952725>

Merulina cylindrica

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322205774>

Montipora

Family: [Acroporidae](#)

Genus: [Montipora](#)

Foliose (c) Chew K.L.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/284188972>

Plate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328576580>

Encrusting/massive

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042021>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/323989289>

Mycedium

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Mycedium](#)

Mycedium mancaoi

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328576609>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/326158574>

Mycedium robokaki

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330204045>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328623420>

Mycedium elephantotus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952697>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330207605>

Oulastrea

Family: [Oulastreidae](#)

Genus: [Oulastrea](#)

Oulastrea crispata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335175719>

Oulophyllia

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Oulophyllia](#)

Oulophyllia bennettiae

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/323439168>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952857>

Oulophyllia crispa, levis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328560821>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/323989133>

Oxypora

Family: [Lobophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Oxypora](#)

Encrusting separate corallites

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/326158565>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/329141137>

Encrusting indistinct corallites

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407717>

Plate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/236218380>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283348437>

Pachyseris

Family: [Pachyseridae](#)

Genus: [Pachyseris](#)

Pachyseris speciosa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330201332>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328576626>

Pachyseris rugosa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/236218350>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/240906191>

Palauastrea

Family: [Astrocoeniidae](#)

Genus: [Palauastrea](#)

Monotypic

Palauastrea ramosa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952923>

Paragoniastrea

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Paragoniastrea](#)

Paragoniastrea russelli

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283379446>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328568286>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328568285>

Pavona

Family: [Agariciidae](#)

Genus: [Pavona](#)

Pavona cactus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283348475>

Pavona densuscata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283379337>

Pavona explanulata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328623438>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322403781>

Pavona frondifera

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/242689068>

Pavona bipartita

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328568268>

Pavona venosa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042115>

Pavona varians

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330207529>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/329141082>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328568131>

Pavona clavus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042460>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322536928>

Pavona duerdeni

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/324344729>

Pectinia

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Pectinia](#)

Branching *Pectinia*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/271174192>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407667>

Pectinia lactuca

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/329141150>

Physogyra

Family: [Plerogyridae](#)

Genus: [Physogyra](#)

A monotypic genus.

Physogyra lichtensteini

- Retracted vesicles: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330206118>
- Extended vesicles: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/237618753>

Platygyra

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Platygyra](#)

Shared corallites

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/329141163>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/329141176>

Meandroid

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330206092>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042173>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092201>

Plerogyra

Family: [Plerogyridae](#)

Genus: [Plerogyra](#)

Plerogyra simplex

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952688>

Plerogyra sinuosa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283348391>

Plerogyra diabolotus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360787>

Pleuractis

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Pleuractis](#)

Pleuractis granulosa

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092026>

Pleuractis moluccensis or *Cantharellus noumeae*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/285006012>

Other *Pleuractis*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360686>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/295027157>

Pocillopora

Family: [Pocilloporidae](#)

Genus: [Pocillopora](#)

Pocillopora acuta, damicornis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328623454>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330204084>

Pocillopora damicornis, verucosa, meandrina

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328576640>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952849>

Pocillopora grandis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328576641>

Podabacia

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Podabacia](#)

Attached plate

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/324344744>

Free-living

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/251407726>

Polyphyllia

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Polyphyllia](#)

Polyphyllia talpina

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/242689001>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952424>

Porites

Family: [Poritidae](#)

Genus: [Porites](#)

Porites cylindrica and other branching species

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952456>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330207512>

Porites deformis or *annae*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092065>

Porites massive

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952646>

Porites rus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/326158513>

Psammocora

Family: [Psammocoridae](#)

Genus: [Psammocora](#)

Psammocora contigua

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/236218361>

Psammocora haimiana

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/324160724>

Psammocora columna

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/269092878>

Psammocora profundacella

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330176334>

Psammocora nierstraszi

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042316>

Pseudosiderastrea

Family: [Rhizangiidae](#)

Genus: [Pseudosiderastrea](#)

Pseudosiderastrea tayamai

<https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360837>

Sandalolitha

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Sandalolitha](#)

Sandalolitha dentata cf.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/280984710>

Sandalolitha robusta cf.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/236218435>

Seriatopora

Family: [Pocilloporidae](#)

Genus: [Seriatopora](#)

Seriatopora hystrix cf.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/236218362>

Seriatopora aculeata cf.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952885>

Stylocoeniella

Family: [Astrocoeniidae](#)

Genus: [Stylocoeniella](#)

Stylocoeniella guentheri

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/349216519>

Stylocoeniella armata

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952807>

Stylophora

Family: [Pocilloporidae](#)

Genus: [Stylophora](#)

Branching clubs

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/328560663>

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/236218354>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/324499493>

Thalamophyllia

Family: [Agariciidae](#)

Genus: [Thalamophyllia](#)

Thalamophyllia tenuescens

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330207538>

Trachyphyllia

Family: [Merulinidae](#)

Genus: [Trachyphyllia](#)

Trachyphyllia geoffroyi

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335360839>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/291466323>

Truncatoflabellum

Family: [Flabellidae](#)

Genus: [Truncatoflabellum](#)

Isolated attached

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/335175701>

Tubastrea

Family: [Dendrophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Tubastrea](#)

Tubastrea micranthus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952736>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322708576>

Tubastrea diaphana

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/283368502>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952880>

Tubastrea coccinea

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/327042049>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/302301160>

Other weird *Tubastrea*

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/333952898>

Turbinaria

Family: [Dendrophyllidae](#)

Genus: [Turbinaria](#)

Turbinaria stelluata cf.

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/322403785>

Turbinaria renniformis

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/321366744>

Turbinaria mesenterina

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/330176345>

Zoopilus

Family: [Fungiidae](#)

Genus: [Zoopilus](#)

Zoopilus echinatus

- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/302307250>
- <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/326158536>

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Veron, J. E. N. (2000). *Corals of the World* (M. Stafford-Smith (ed.)). Australian Institute of Marine Science.